

AN INNOVATIVE SYSTEM FOR RAINWATER HARVESTING AND STORAGE THROUGH FLEXIBLE WATER TANKS

Pari L.^{1*}, Stefanoni W.¹, Latterini F.¹, Suardi A.¹, Palmieri N.¹, Alfano V.¹, Bergonzoli S.², Lazar S.¹

¹Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria, Unità di ricerca per l'ingegneria agraria – Monterotondo (Rome-Italy) luigi.pari@crea.gov.it; walter.stefanoni@crea.gov.it; francesco.latterini@crea.gov.it; alessandro.suardi@crea.gov.it; nadia.palmieri@crea.gov.it; vincenzo.alfano@crea.gov.it; sandu.lazar@crea.gov.it

²Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria, Unità di ricerca per l'ingegneria agraria – Treviglio (Bergamo-Italy) simone.bergonzoli@crea.gov.it

*Correspondance: Luigi Pari, luigi.pari@crea.gov.it

ABSTRACT: Climate change is strongly affecting agriculture worldwide. In Mediterranean zone one of the most challenging issue is related to water deficit as a consequence of climate change. In particular, in Mediterranean Countries, we are facing a higher number of extreme rain events during winter and, on the other hand, a much more lasting and stronger drought during summer. A possible solution to increase the ability of agriculture sector to face such problems relies in being able to collect excess water during winter in order to use it for irrigation during drought period. The present study aims to compare an innovative prototype of flexible water tank able to store rain water with the traditional artificial basin storage solutions, in order to use this for irrigation during summer period.

Keywords: environmental impacts; cost analysis; run-off; pond; flexible water storage system

1 INTRODUCTION

Agriculture sector is one of the main responsible of freshwater consumption in Europe. Agriculture accounts indeed for the 24% of the abstracted water, percentage which can reach 80% in Southern regions [1]. Water scarcity is further enhanced by climate change, mostly in the Mediterranean region, where heavy rainfall events are occurring with higher frequency but in shorter period during the year [2]. Considering what written above, there is growing in arid and semi-arid region of the planet concerning the possibility to collect and store rainwater for urban and agriculture purposes [3].

Rain water harvesting (RWH) is the process of accumulating rainfall with the help of several systems [4]. RWH has been applied for centuries to meet water supply needs and nowadays can still represent an important practice to improve the water use efficiency [3]. Rainfall storage can be achieved with various types of storage systems that can also differ remarkably in terms of costs and environmental impacts [3].

Considering what reported above, authors analyzed the environmental and economic performance of a conventional water storage system, i.e. a pond, in comparison to an innovative Flexible Water Storage System (FWSS). This innovative system brings about practical advantages to farmers, as a consequence of its flexibility and the easy-to-move feature. A comparison was carried out via LCA and LCC assessment starting for the hypothesis that 400 m³ of rainwater can be collected and stored locally for crop irrigation purpose.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

A schematic representation of the two different water storage systems investigated in this work is given in Figure 1.

Ponds represent the typical rainwater storage system, mainly thanks to their easiness of building [5]. However, there are several drawbacks, for instance permanent disturbance of the soil, reduction of the arable surface, concerns related to water quality and safety. In order to store the assumed 400 m³ of water, authors made the hypothesis of removing an equivalent volume of soil

(336.6 m² and 1.4 m depth) by using a 90-kW excavator. According to the estimations, digging requires 20.5 h and 328.1 l of fuel. Consequently, a double layer 1350 g m⁻² PVC is applied.

Figure 1: Schematic view of Pond (A) and FWSS (B) in a theoretical agroforestry plant. Numbers refer to the main components of both systems: (1) seasonal water stream, (2) loading system (including electric pump, pipes and connections), (3) water storage system, (4) electric pump for water delivery, (5) water usage (e.g., irrigation system).

An innovative alternative to ponds consists of Flexible Water Storage System (FWSS). The FWSS consists of an envelope of polyvinyl chloride (PVC) 930 g m⁻² thick and equipped with inlet and outlet pipe connections. Loading operation is carried out via electric water pump which can draw from a near seasonal water stream directly into the FWSS. When the tank reaches its maximum capacity, the blow-off valve opens preventing over-pressure. Storage of water can be as long as it is needed without leak of water or smell. This system can be moved according to the needs of the farmer; the installation does not require a concrete base. Contrary to the Pond, water is not in direct contact with sunlight; therefore microbial activities are not promoted.

A comparison of the environmental performance of these systems was performed via Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) and Life Cycle Cost (LCC), similarly to previous studies in agriculture sector [6].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Results of LCA are given in Figure 2. As it is possible to notice pond system showed higher impact than FWSS for all the investigated parameters.

Figure 2: Result of the characterization, comparison of two different runoff water storage systems with functional unit of 1 m³ of storable water. The values are expressed as percentages in relation to the 100% given to RWH systems with the biggest impact in each category (i.e., Pond=100% in all the considered impact categories). The acronyms of the different impact categories are CCHH (Climate change Human Health), OD (Ozone depletion), HT (Human toxicity), POF (Photochemical oxidant formation), PMF (Particulate matter formation), IR (Ionizing radiation), CCE (Climate change Ecosystems), TA (Terrestrial acidification), FE (Freshwater eutrophication), TE (Terrestrial ecotoxicity), FRE (Freshwater ecotoxicity), ME (Marine ecotoxicity), ALO (Agricultural land occupation), ULO (Urban land occupation), NLT (Natural land transformation), MD (Metal depletion), FD (Fossil depletion).

Focusing on economic aspects, FWSS showed also in this case better performance than pond, with 16.94 € m⁻³ of storable water; versus 20.41 € m⁻³ of the Pond system. Finally, the highest value of the carbon footprint was shown by Pond system, while FWSS system led to lower value of GHG emission and aggregated costs. Our findings showed as FWSS system was the best solution regarding economic and environmental point of view. In fact, FWSS and Pond systems cost 16.94 € with an emission of 17.4 gr CO₂ eq per m³ of storable water and 20.41 € with an emission of 28.2 gr CO₂ eq per m³ of storable water, respectively.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The goal of the present work was to perform an environmental and economic analysis of two different RWH systems for irrigation purposes. LCA and LCC were carried out to compare a typical pond for water storage and an innovative flexible water storage system (FWSS). The findings revealed that FWSS system showed better performance under both environmental and economic aspects, resulting in a suitable and sustainable solution for water harvesting in agriculture.

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